

LISTING REQUIREMENTS OF THE LARGEST STOCK EXCHANGES

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One of the most common forms of investment in the world is buying stocks. due to the fact that investing in JSC securities requires less cash and may be done more quickly than foreign direct investment. Securities investments, which comprise different assets including stocks, bonds, and their derivatives, are referred to as portfolio investments. Acquiring assets listed on a stock exchange, a specialized trading venue, is how portfolio investments are created.

Throughout the world, hundreds of stock exchanges have been founded and are currently running profitably. Stock exchanges have been around for more than 50 years. There are still exchanges in operation today that were founded in the middle of the 19th century and toward the end of the 20th century. The world's top stock exchanges include those in Frankfurt, Hong Kong, New York, London, and Hong Kong.

The official stock exchange listing of JSC implies a certain degree of dependability and financial stability for these businesses, and the ongoing release of information about them boosts investor trust in making investments [1].

The development of global financial hubs and their acceptance on a global scale have expanded JSC's areas of operation and resource bases [2].

Fifty percent of all worldwide stock trading happens on the London Stock Exchange (LSE), one of the global stock exchanges. The primary currency transacted on this exchange is pounds sterling. There are two divisions within the London Stock Exchange:

Main (approved firms are those who fulfill the UK Financial Conduct Authority's standards);

Alternative (far less demanding, meant for new businesses to join the market).

Large firms use the main market as a stock exchange platform, and as of April 2023, 1,918 JSC were listed on the stock exchange. As of August 2023, the total market capitalization is £3.18 trillion. When JSC are listed on the main market, they become recognized as top global firms and get interest from potential investors. The market is appealing to businesses and investors because of its high standards—which aren't overly rigid.

Emerging enterprises can trade on the Alternative Investment Market (AIM). It was introduced in 1995 and has since grown to be the fastest-growing market

globally, helping over 2,000 businesses to fund more than £20 billion. A simplified regulatory structure designed to meet the needs of small and developing JSC is fundamental to AIM's success.

Based in the United States, the New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) is one of the biggest stock exchanges globally. This stock exchange gave rise to the renowned Dow Jones index (Dow Jones Industrial Average), which was formed for shares of industrial businesses. The primary currency transacted on this exchange is US dollars.

The largest electronic stock exchange in the world is called NASDAQ. Ten percent or so of the 3,200 firms that have been listed there are international issuers. Leading businesses in industries such technology, retail, communications, finance, media services, transportation, and biotechnology are listed on the NASDAQ. Only this exchange sees trading of more than 50% of the shares listed on the NASDAQ market.

With the advent of NASDAQ, the NYSE had competition in the late 1980s and early 1990s. While the majority of American markets remained closed in 1992, trading on the electronic exchange was permitted. As a result, the amount of trading on the NASDAQ grew, and traders were able to do business throughout European market hours. Furthermore, NASDAQ has assisted enterprises in raising the funds necessary to run and develop their operations when they don't fit the rigid criteria for a NYSE listing. The activities of businesses worldwide who operate in the communication and information technology sector have undergone significant changes as a result of NASDAQ.

The NYSE and the NASDAQ have been engaged in a heated race to host initial public offerings (IPOs) of both domestic and international firms since the mid-1990s. The majority of them decided to arrange IPOs on the NASDAQ stock exchange. The NYSE even built an office close to Silicon Valley to recruit young, high-tech firms in an attempt to address the matter.

The New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) implemented a new stock quote system in 2000 with the goal of luring overseas corporations. This system was the first to replace fractions with decimals in line with the global exchanges' established practice. Building on its lengthy history and solid reputation, it increased its advertising budget by double in the late 1990s. But even in the early 21st century, there were still claims that the NYSE had become irrelevant and that the auction system it employed was out of date. The primary distinction between the NASDAQ and the NYSE is the trading format. The NASDAQ uses computerized methods to do this task, but the NYSE relies on the actions of experienced dealers

who choose buy and sell orders that complement one another in terms of pricing. Since 1992, 82% of all firms that have gone public have traded on NASDAQ. 69% of all foreign businesses that entered the US market made use of this exchange's services.

The stock exchange in Hong Kong (HK Stock Exchange). When it comes to listed firms' capitalization, the stock market is ranked seventh. US and Hong Kong dollars are the trading currency. One of the two stock markets—the primary market or the market for growing firms—is where corporations can list their shares [3].

The Frankfurt Stock market, often known as the Frankfurter Wertpapierbörse or simply FWB, is the biggest stock market in Germany and among the biggest globally. The euro is the trading currency. Issuers may list on the Frankfurt Stock Exchange in the General Standard or Prime Standard sectors, which are subject to EU laws, as of January 1, 2003. Furthermore, issuers may choose to list in one of two segments—the entry standard or the first quotation board—and on the Frankfurt Stock Exchange, which is governed by the exchange itself.

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